

Roadmap
for the European
Virtual Human Twin
Policy brief

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EDITH

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This document is the **extended summary of the roadmap for the Virtual Human Twin**, containing the main elements in terms of context, vision, building blocks, and recommendations for the realization of the VHT. The VHT roadmap is a deliverable of the EDITH project. EDITH, “Ecosystem for digital twins in healthcare”, was a coordination and support action funded by the Digital Europe program (grant number 101083771) that brought together the entire ecosystem working on activities related to the Virtual Human Twin in the broadest sense. The full version of the roadmap is available at: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14769224>.

Further information on the EU Virtual Human Twin Initiative is available on the website of the European Commission: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/virtual-human-twins>

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Methodology and validation

The roadmapping process has been divided in three main phases: design (10/2022-7/2023), develop (8/2023-7/2024) and deliver (8/2024-12/2024). Through a wide range of ecosystem activities, from surveys over targeted focus groups to large public meetings, the EDITH consortium has coordinated the writing of a roadmap detailing the steps required to successfully realize the potential of the Virtual Human Twin initiative and infrastructure. **Over 800 people were involved in EDITH activities, events and roadmap writing**, while many more have been involved in VHT-related discussions at scientific conferences, policy events, outreach activities and a wide variety of trainings.

To **validate the resulting roadmap, following key principles were observed**¹:

- **Need identification:** the roadmap identifies and addresses existing gaps in programs;
- **Understanding:** the roadmap structure and contents are developed to facilitate comprehension;
- **Acceptability:** the roadmap process has been conducted with attention for perception, satisfactoriness and fit in the current context;
- **Integration:** the roadmap is fit for integration into the current programming across all stakeholders;
- **Translation:** facilitators of translation such as appropriateness, context nuances and budget feasibility have been investigated and addressed;
- **Implementation:** possible execution of all sections and actions is listed in the roadmap;
- **Practicality:** existing financial instruments and human resources have been identified to implement the roadmap;
- **Political buy-in:** the political support for implementation of the roadmap (from individual organizations up to EU level) is present and is continuously being extended.

Finally, the whole process of roadmapping has been **supervised and validated by the Advisory Group of Stakeholders**, a group of high-level renowned experts from academia (engineering, sciences, social sciences, humanities and law), industry (companies and trade organisations), healthcare sector, regulatory agencies and patients organisations.

Roadmap

The roadmap will be available on the EDITH community² in the European open access repository Zenodo, as well as on www.virtualhumantwins.eu. While this extended summary contains the main arguments and recommendations, the technical details of each topic can be found in the roadmap. Additionally, a range of use cases, user stories, success stories and EDITH realisation reports, provide illustration to the different concepts discussed.

PART 1: FROM DIGITAL TWINS IN HEALTHCARE TO THE VIRTUAL HUMAN TWIN

Introduction

Digital Twins in health and care

A **Digital Twin (DT)** is the virtual representation of a physical object or system across its lifecycle. It uses real-time data and other sources to enable learning, reasoning, and dynamically recalibrating for monitoring, diagnostics, and prognostics. When applied in the context of health and care, the elements of real-time read-out and dynamic recalibration are relevant for specific applications and contexts (such as ICU patient care and deep brain stimulation), but for many other applications these elements are not feasible and/or needed. Hence, for most applications in health and care, the interactions between the Digital Twin and its physical counterpart are realized through a human-in-the-loop³. Hence, the concept of **Digital Twins in healthcare**, also indicated with the term Virtual Human Twins, is extended to the direct use of individual-specific models for the prevention, prediction, screening, diagnosis and treatment of a disease, as well as the evaluation, optimization, selection and personalisation of intervention options.

Digital Twins can focus on pathophysiological processes at **multiple time and length scales**, from a single cell over tissues to the organ or system level, or **treatment strategies** (devices, drugs or advanced therapies). In addition, Digital Twins can also cover **manufacturing processes** related to the aforementioned therapeutic strategies, or even entire **medical facilities**. Henceforth, when the term DT is used, it is understood to be one of the aforementioned applications.

The key potential in health and care of this technology is related to targeted prevention, tailored clinical pathways, and to supporting healthcare professionals in virtual environments. Examples include implementation of clinical trials for medicines and devices, medical training, surgical intervention planning, and several other potential use cases in virtual world environments.

The Virtual Human Twin

Virtual Human Twins hold great potential in **advancing personalised care**, a core priority for the European Union. They will accelerate tangible **benefits for citizens and patients**, while also **sustaining and advancing EU science and technology**. Virtual Human Twin initiatives exist across many Member States. Academia, large industry, and SME innovators have already developed different versions of them in collaboration with clinicians, healthcare providers, and other stakeholders. However, while the number of interested stakeholders is growing, the ecosystem remains highly fragmented in the EU.

The **Virtual Human Twin (VHT) initiative**, officially launched by the European Commission on December 21st 2023⁴ **aims to tackle this fragmentation** on all levels. Conceptually, the VHT is to be a systematic, ever-growing digital, and quantitative representation of the actionable knowledge available on human pathophysiology. This entails, amongst others, the creation of a **federated public infrastructure** that will enable the pooling and linking of resources and assets (data, models, algorithms, computing power, storage, etc.), facilitating the development of Digital Twins in healthcare and the assessment of their credibility. This will require **continued support** for advanced research, technology development and platform operation, leveraging the power of supercomputers and Digital Twin technologies, including AI, and supporting interoperability, integration and the scaling up of DT-based solutions. These developments need to take place in full **compliance with EU values and rules** related to privacy, safety and security. In addition, realising the VHT will require an **engaged ecosystem**, which fosters inclusion and collaboration among diverse stakeholders.

Global trends in a European context

The healthcare landscape, both in Europe and across the globe, is undergoing a profound transformation, fuelled by an array of interconnected global trends. These trends underscore the need for novel healthcare solutions, with the VHT emerging as a particularly promising concept. The VHT holds the potential to address critical healthcare challenges and propel the industry towards a more personalized, sustainable, and effective future.

Trend 1:

Escalating healthcare costs, workforce shortage and the need for efficiency

Globally, healthcare costs are rising at an unsustainable pace, straining healthcare systems and economies. This surge in expenditures is driven by multiple factors, including:

- **Aging populations:** as life expectancy increases, the proportion of older adults in the global population is growing⁵, leading to a higher demand for healthcare services. Older individuals often have more complex healthcare needs, contributing to higher healthcare costs.
- **Chronic and complex diseases:** the prevalence of chronic and complex diseases, such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes, is increasing worldwide⁶. Managing these conditions often requires managing multiple morbidities, as well as long-term and costly care, therefore placing significant financial burdens on healthcare systems.
- **Advances in medical technology:** while advancements in medical technology have led to improved treatments and diagnostic tools, these innovations often come with high price tags, contributing to the overall rise in healthcare costs.
- **Workforce shortages:** many countries are facing a growing shortage of healthcare workers, exacerbated by an aging workforce⁷. This shortage places additional strain on existing personnel, reduces system efficiency, and increases the cost of delivering care due to over-reliance on temporary staff or outsourcing.

The escalating healthcare costs necessitate a shift towards more efficient healthcare systems. The VHT can strongly contribute to a potential solution by enabling:

- **Prevention and early disease detection:** through continuous monitoring and analysis of individual health data, the VHT could facilitate the early detection of disease risk biomarkers and enable prevention and early treatment, potentially reducing the need for costly treatments later on. For instance, the Dutch MyDigiTwin project⁸ provides a platform where patients' self-reported data is combined with data from their healthcare providers, and compared through AI-based algorithms with existing records, allowing patients to check and monitor their health and identify possible risks of various cardiovascular diseases.
- **Personalized treatment optimization:** by creating personalized models of individual patients, the VHT could help clinicians optimize treatment plans, reducing the likelihood of adverse reactions and improving the effectiveness of therapies, thus leading to cost savings. A wide range of DT-based surgical planning tools are currently in clinical use where critical choices (e.g. type and placement of stents) can be tested *in silico*.
- **Optimising development and delivery processes:** by creating virtual populations, the VHT could facilitate *in silico* clinical trials (i.e. trials executed in the computer) to complement and optimise *in vivo* clinical trials. Models of healthcare workflows and resource distribution (e.g. bed allocation), allow to optimise the overall logistics of the healthcare process.

Trend 2:

The imperative for personalized medicine

There is a growing need for personalised medicine, a paradigm that tailors medical care to individual patients based on their unique characteristics. The healthcare industry is transitioning towards this paradigm. Personalized medicine aims to move away from a one-size-fits-all approach to healthcare which acknowledges that individuals respond differently to treatments and interventions. This shift is driven by the understanding of the following elements:

- **Genetic and structural variation:** individuals possess unique genetic variations as well as structural variations (particularly in the brain, such as the connectome) that influence their susceptibility to diseases and their responses to medications.
- **Lifestyle factors and social determinants:** lifestyle factors, such as diet and exercise, and social determinants, such as income and education, also play a significant role in health and disease.
- **Exposome:** environmental exposures, such as pollution, and the effects of climate change have been shown to affect patients' health.
- **Individual health history:** each patient has a unique health history that informs their current and future healthcare needs.

The VHT can serve as a powerful tool for strongly accelerating innovations required for advancing personalized medicine by:

- **Integrating multi-modal data:** the VHT can facilitate the seamless and automatic integration of data from various sources, including electronic health records, genetic tests, wearable sensors, and imaging studies, to create a comprehensive and personalized model of each patient.
- **Simulating treatment responses:** using the personalized model, clinicians can virtually test on a computer how a patient might respond to different treatment options, enabling them to select the most effective and personalized approach.
- **Monitoring individual responses:** the VHT can (continuously) monitor patient responses to treatments and interventions, allowing for adjustments to treatment plans based on individual needs.

Trend 3:

The rise of digitalization in healthcare

The healthcare system is experiencing rapid digitalization, with the adoption of electronic health records (EHRs), telehealth, mobile health (mHealth) applications, wearable sensors, and AI. This digital transformation offers numerous opportunities to improve healthcare delivery, including:

- **Enhanced data collection and analysis:** digital technologies, in combination with advanced computing infrastructures and services, facilitate the collection, storage, and analysis of vast amounts of health data, providing insights into population health trends and individual patient characteristics, leading to more informed decision-making.
- **Improved patient engagement:** mHealth apps and wearable sensors empower patients to take a more active role in managing their own health, promoting self-monitoring and adherence to treatment plans.

- **Improved access to care:** telehealth and remote patient monitoring technologies enable healthcare providers to monitor patients outside of traditional clinical settings, improving access to care and reducing healthcare costs.

The VHT can effectively leverage advancements in digital healthcare in a number of key ways:

- **Advancing health and eHealth research:** the VHT and its infrastructure will allow the pooling and linking of resources and assets (data, models, algorithms, computing power, storage, etc.), facilitating the development of Digital Twins in healthcare and the assessment of their credibility.
- **Accelerated therapy development:** patient populations created using the VHT can simulate clinical trials in a virtual environment. This application could potentially accelerate drug and device development, and as a result, reduce costs associated with traditional clinical trials.
- **Holistic view of patient health:** by integrating data from various digital health sources, the VHT can create a comprehensive and dynamic view of each patient's health status.
- **Predictive analytics and proactive care:** AI algorithms can be incorporated into the VHT to analyse patterns in individuals' health data, predicting disease risks and treatment outcomes. This predictive capability allows for more proactive and personalized healthcare interventions.

Trend 4:

The EU digital agenda and infrastructures

The EU is actively promoting the development of digital health technologies through initiatives such as the EU Digital Agenda. These initiatives focus on:

- **Fostering innovation in digital health:** the EU supports research and development in digital health technologies, including initiatives related to the VHT.
- **Developing digital health infrastructures:** the EU is investing in creating digital health infrastructures, such as those established under the European Health Data Space (EHDS), which will support the secure and ethical sharing of health data. This infrastructure will be essential for developing and deploying the VHT effectively.
- **Organizing digital knowledge:** the EU is developing infrastructures for knowledge organisation such as EBRAINS and EUCAIM, which integrate and interoperate domain-specific data, models, and/or tools, as well as providing the operational basis of VHT.
- **Establishing regulatory frameworks:** the EU has been developing regulatory frameworks, on top of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), such as the AI Act, the Data Governance Act and the European Health Data Space (EHDS), also to ensure the responsible and ethical use of digital health technologies, including the VHT.

The European life sciences research infrastructures, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), European infrastructure for translational medicine (EATRIS) and the European life sciences infrastructure (ELIXIR), can play a vital role in supporting VHT development. These infrastructures provide access to:

- **Data and biobanks:** researchers can access a wide range of health data and biological samples to develop and validate VHT models. For instance, ELIXIR provides access to biological data, analysis tools, and computational resources, supporting research in fields such as genomics, proteomics, and systems biology. EOSC provides access to a wealth of data and research outputs from various fields. The VHT should utilize these resources to access and analyse large datasets, develop sophisticated models of human biology, and accelerate the development of VHT applications.

- **Computational resources:** advanced computing infrastructures are essential for running complex VHT simulations. The EuroHPC Joint Undertaking was established to coordinate efforts between the EU and the participating countries for pooling resources and leading European supercomputing initiatives.
- **Expertise and collaboration:** research infrastructures foster collaboration between scientists from different disciplines and between stakeholders, which is crucial for the interdisciplinary and intersectoral nature of VHT research. For instance, EATRIS supports the translation of research discoveries into clinical practice, facilitating collaboration between researchers, clinicians, and industry partners. The VHT leverages expertise and infrastructure from EATRIS and other life sciences research infrastructures to bridge the gap between research and clinical implementation, ensuring that VHT-based innovations reach patients and healthcare providers effectively.

Trend 5:

Contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outline a global agenda for achieving a more sustainable and equitable future⁹.

The VHT can play a role in achieving several SDGs, particularly those related to:

- **Good health and well-being (SDG 3):** by improving patient care, overall experiences and healthcare outcomes, promoting preventative care, and enabling personalized medicine, the VHT can contribute to ensuring healthy lives and well-being for all ages.
- **Gender equality (SDG 5):** the VHT can be used to study the effects of sex differences on health and disease, and to develop more effective treatments for all patients. *In silico* clinical trials can be used to design or augment clinical trials ensuring an adequate representation of the entire population.
- **Reduced inequalities (SDG 10):** the VHT can contribute to ensuring equitable access to healthcare by providing personalized and cost-effective solutions that are accessible to individuals regardless of their socioeconomic status or geographic location. For instance, the VHT can provide a virtual training environment to novice clinicians or non-clinicians who provide care at remote locations that otherwise have limited or no access to state-of-the-art information and healthcare.

The need for the Virtual Human Twin initiative and infrastructure

Convergence of global healthcare needs and trends is exposing the limits of traditional approaches to innovation, which are often reactive and one-size-fits-all, and provides a strong rationale for development of the VHT. The **VHT offers a transformative approach to healthcare**, addressing the challenges of rising healthcare costs, the demand for personalized medicine, and the need for more efficient and effective healthcare systems. By leveraging the power of digitalization, aligning with EU policy initiatives, the VHT holds the promise of a healthier and more sustainable future for individuals and societies worldwide.

At the heart of the VHT initiative lies the **transformative power of *in silico* technologies**, including computer modelling and simulation as well as artificial intelligence. These are supported by the **indispensable hardware developments** related to computational infrastructure as well as data generation, storage and transport technologies. By creating virtual representations of human physiology and pathology through the use of human-relevant and patient-specific data, researchers and clinicians can gain unprecedented scientific insights into the complexities of the human body and disease progression across length scales, time scales, and organ systems. These insights can then be leveraged towards providing personalized, predictive and preventive care, accelerate medical research and innovation, and improve support for clinicians, healthcare providers and patients. It is important to remark that both the gathering of new knowledge as well as its application in improving clinical care, are important objectives of the VHT.

The ambitious vision of the VHT requires a collaborative effort that transcends national boundaries. Establishing a European VHT infrastructure would allow a series of benefits, including:

- **Pooling resources and expertise:** Europe possesses a wealth of scientific, clinical and industrial expertise, R&D and healthcare organisations, and healthcare data. A European infrastructure can effectively pool these resources, facilitating collaboration and knowledge sharing among diverse stakeholders, including researchers, technology developers, clinicians, patients, regulators and policymakers.
- **Data sharing and interoperability:** a European infrastructure can address the challenges of data fragmentation and interoperability of data, models, and tools that hinder VHT development. Establishing common standards and protocols for data sharing and model development ensures seamless data integration across national borders and facilitates the creation of comprehensive VHT models.
- **Credibility and trust:** a centralized European infrastructure can play a vital role in establishing the credibility and trustworthiness of VHT technologies. Implementing robust validation and verification processes, adhering to ethical guidelines and involving regulatory bodies ensures that VHT models are accurate, reliable and meet the highest scientific and ethical standards.
- **Economic benefits:** a thriving VHT ecosystem can drive economic growth and create new opportunities for European industry and innovation. By fostering collaboration between academia, industry, and healthcare providers, the VHT initiative can stimulate the development of new technologies, products, and services in the healthcare sector, enhancing Europe's global competitiveness.

Current status of the Virtual Human Twin

While integrated Digital Twins – which bridge multiple organs and/or time and length scales – remain largely confined to the research stage, there are ample examples of the implementation of Twin technologies in Healthcare across various medical fields, focusing on specific organs or diseases, ensuring the initiative can build on a rich and diverse foundation. Figure 1 shows a number of examples¹⁰, illustrating the use of Digital Twins in clinical decision support systems, surgical planning tools, *in silico* (clinical) trials and as a research instrument to enhance our insights in complex diseases.

Pharmacogenomic twins¹¹: patient-specific twins built on clinical routine data and multiomics (e.g., RNA sequencing) data, down to the single cell level.
Application: drug discovery, drug safety, personalisation and dosing.
Deployed: in clinical testing/use.

Universal Immune System Simulator¹²: agent-based model of immune system including dynamics of relevant cell types and signalling pathways.
Application: optimizing therapeutic strategies, drug regimens, and outcomes for a range of diseases including Tuberculosis, MS, COVID-19 and others.
Deployed: clinically validated, EMA letter of recommendation. Start-up.

Virtual Twins for cancers¹³: integrating molecular, cellular, and tissue scales using omics and imaging data to create personalized tumour models.
Application: improve prognosis and identify patient-specific therapies with optimized dosages and combinations.
Deployed: research.

Figure 1: VHT state of the art. These examples are a few of many developments at different Technology Readiness Levels, going from basic research to clinical uptake. Further information on the examples shown here can be found in references (11-18).

Virtual Brain Twin¹⁴: personalizable brain model derived from an individual's own brain imaging data.
Application: epilepsy, neurodegenerative diseases, schizophrenia, development and ageing, and sleep.
Deployed: brain simulator in the EBRAINS infrastructure.

Virtual Heart Twins¹⁵: personalizable heart model derived from heart imaging and ECG data, and/or mechanistic info on biological, mechanical and/or electrical aspects.
Application: clinical decision support, surgery planning and evaluation.
Deployed: various twins used in clinical practice, start-ups with reimbursement established.

Glycemic control in ICU¹⁶: combining metabolic mechanisms with AI-based personalisation. Local, real-time bed-side software supporting EHR integration.
Application: clinical decision support solution for ICU patients, preventing hyper- and hypo-glycemia, speeding up recovery.
Deployed: in clinical trials, start-up established.

Virtual Liver Twins¹⁷: personalizable imaging-based liver models capturing liver haemodynamics and deformation during surgery.
Application: liver resection surgery planning.
Deployed: tested in patient cohorts.

Virtual Bone Twin¹⁸: personalised imaging-based models of the hip region for osteoporotic patients.
Application: patient-specific hip fracture risk prediction. Design of therapeutic strategies for improving osteoporotic drug effectiveness.
Deployed: clinical research studies.

Stakeholders of the Virtual Human Twin

Realising the potential of the VHT is beyond the capabilities of any individual organization or even community (e.g. *in silico* medicine, wearables, organ-on-chip), but rather requires establishing and **engaging the entire ecosystem**. The concept of ecosystems encompasses the intricate interconnections between various sectors and stakeholders. The VHT ecosystem includes all participants along the VHT's value chain, including academic and research organisations, industrial organisations from the smallest start-up to the largest corporations, healthcare professionals, patients, regulators, health authorities, payers, policymakers, and more. The figure below provides an overview of the VHT Community of Practice, starting from the VHT beneficiaries and users identifying the need, over VHT creators developing solutions and VHT enablers providing the necessary infrastructure and resources, to the VHT managers responsible for its governance. Figure 2 and the following paragraphs summarize the different actors and their role in the VHT¹⁹

Figure 2: VHT ecosystem. ELSI: Ethical, Legal, Social issues; CSO: Civil Society Organisation.

Patients and citizens are beneficiaries and users of VHT technologies, who are central to the VHT ecosystem. They are involved in co-developing and co-assessing VHT technologies. Patient and citizen groups are end users or beneficiaries of Digital Twins in Healthcare, where DTs are addressing an unmet clinical need.

Healthcare professionals and systems are users, beneficiaries and co-creators of VHT technologies, with oversight on safety-risk-benefit-harms and adverse events. They are involved in identifying unmet need, developing, assessing (clinical/regulatory/reimbursement) and adopting VHT technologies within healthcare systems.

Research and innovation actors are creators/developers of the VHT with a focus on basic research and innovation of VHT technologies, beyond state of the art. They are furthermore involved in developing regulatory and evidence science, governance framework including ELSI, liaising as expert assessors and appraiser of VHT technologies and their impact across the entire health continuum. Likewise, the research innovation actors fill the role of independent reference laboratories or testing centres, as well as conducting clinical research studies in collaboration with academic medical centres and industrial actors.

Industry plays an important role in the creation and development of the VHT with a focus on applied research, development and industrialization of VHT technologies, in compliance with standards, regulations, legislative and societal guardrails. They are furthermore involved in the practice of regulatory and evidence science, governance frameworks throughout the lifecycle and ecosystem of VHT technologies. There is a wide range of industrial profiles relevant for the VHT: from software product developers, over equipment manufacturers to DT sellers, distributors and marketers.

Infrastructure actors for data, research and computing are VHT enablers or orchestrators who facilitate the effective design, development, implementation, deployment and maintenance of VHT technologies, in compliance to standards and regulations. They are important in the co-development of the VHT, empowering end-users and beneficiaries of the ecosystem to access the VHT technology in practice.

Technology investors, accelerators, governmental and non-governmental funding agencies fund the development of innovative VHT technologies. They provide mentorship, coaching, and incentives to support the successful development of the first generation of VHT solutions. Their activities can be public, private or through public-private partnerships. They streamline and optimize the innovation pathway within the VHT ecosystem to effectively address unmet healthcare needs.

Policy and law makers are governing and funding actors, who draft and enact governance mechanisms through policies, legislations and public funding that regulate yet incentivize the development of VHT technologies for the safety, wellbeing and benefits of the citizens and the wider society. They are **enablers** that formulate policies, guidance and recommendations for fostering the entire VHT ecosystem that aligns all actors of the VHT community of practice to work towards the common goal.

Regulators, standardization actors, testing and clinical trial actors are governing actors of the VHT who implement the governance instruments set out to test, standardize, regulate and facilitate the market access of VHT technologies developed by the VHT developers, such that the safety and efficacy of the technologies are assured and they do not cause harm to users and beneficiaries (patients and citizens). They formulate guidelines to interpret and apply the legislative acts that govern VHT technologies.

Payers, buyers, reimbursement decision-makers, as well as Health Technology Assessors are funders and governing actors of the VHT who implement the governance instruments set out to evaluate the evidence to support the clinical and economic effectiveness of VHT technologies. This ensures the safety and benefit of said technologies, bringing value and benefits to healthcare systems and broader society (patients and citizens). They are enablers, who streamline the VHT ecosystem, such that the VHT creators/developers from the supply-side of the VHT ecosystem, meet the needs of the demand side from healthcare systems and society.

Legal, IP, Ethical and Social (ELSI) actors include national and EU Parliaments, Competent supervisory Authorities and Courts, Member States and European regulatory and harmonization bodies guiding and regulating the VHT ecosystem by addressing the legal, ethical, social, and intellectual property aspects of the VHT. These actors lay down the applicable legal framework and ensure compliance with laws, foster ethical decision-making, and address societal implications to build trust and acceptance of VHT solutions. They also include legal counsels, Data Protection Officers, compliance officers, AI and social science experts and ethicists, supporting the VHT community in navigating complex legal and social frameworks, while promoting equity, inclusiveness, and moral responsibility in the development, deployment, and application of Digital Twin technologies.

Professional associations serve as crucial catalysts within the VHT ecosystem, facilitating cross-fertilization among diverse stakeholders. By fostering a shared understanding of common goals and priorities, these associations play a vital role in guiding the community towards collective success. By acting as local champions, professional associations inspire their members to embrace the VHT revolution. They effectively bridge the gap between the community and broader stakeholders by gathering and disseminating valuable insights, including emerging challenges and unanswered questions.

Education, training, communication actors create educational resources, develop and disseminate high-quality educational materials, including lectures, online courses, and interactive tools, to broaden public understanding and facilitate self-learning about Digital Twin technologies. One important educational goal is to develop the future workforce: train the next generation of researchers, developers, and practitioners in the creation, utilization, and interpretation of Digital Twin technologies. Another important goal is to educate the public, to inform and engage the broader public about the potential benefits and implications of the VHT, fostering understanding and acceptance within society.

Current and future market appraisal

The global DT in healthcare market is projected to experience significant growth, reaching USD 21.11 billion by 2028 from USD 1.63 billion in 2023²⁰. This growth is driven by several factors. Both public and private entities are **investing** in DT research, development, and infrastructure. The rise of telemedicine and remote patient monitoring is driving the demand for DT technologies to facilitate virtual consultations and personalized care. Finally, continuous advancements in AI, machine learning, and other *in silico* technologies, as well as advancements in relevant hardware, including computing power, imaging and sensor technologies, are enhancing the capabilities and accuracy of digital twins. While there is a disparity in the current use of digital twins in healthcare, the projected growth is similar across the globe (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Geographical snapshot of Digital Twins in the Healthcare market²¹.

Barriers to the wider adoption of the Virtual Human Twin

Despite the consensus on the transformative potential of Digital Twins in Healthcare in medical research, healthcare delivery, and patient care, there are still substantial barriers hindering its widespread translation and adoption as discussed above. These barriers can be grouped into broader categories related to data, technology, ethical, legal and social considerations, economic and sustainability factors, as well as clinical uptake and adoption. Whereas some barriers are highly specific to the VHT itself, others are related to the specific European context in which it will operate²².

1. Data-related barriers

- **Data availability and quality:** the development and validation of reliable VHT models require large volumes of accessible, high-quality and diverse data. The lack of high-quality and properly annotated data poses a significant challenge.
- **Data collection and harmonisation:** there is a lack of standardized or even consensus-driven protocols for data collection and processing, hindering consistency and reliability in data production. Implementation of rigorous quality control measures at each stage of the data lifecycle, coupled with the adoption of clear metadata standards, is required to further enhance data transparency and reproducibility.
- **Data interoperability and standardization:** integrating data from disparate sources with varying formats and standards is crucial for building comprehensive VHT applications. Lack of interoperability and standardization in these collaborative research environments where data is integrated, can lead to potential errors, misinterpretations, and compromised outcomes.

2. Software and infrastructure barriers

- **Software tools and models:** the VHT infrastructure needs robust software tools and models for DT development, simulation, visualization, and data management. These tools and models should follow the FAIR (findable, accessible, inter-operable and reusable) principles to avoid expending valuable resources reinventing the wheel.
- **Model complexity and integration:** developing and validating multi-scale and/or multi-organ VHT models that accurately represent the complexity of human physiology and pathology can be computationally intensive and requires advanced modelling and inference techniques. While running these integrated models through orchestrations of sub-models or data flows offers potential solutions, they face challenges in computational efficiency, interoperability, and tool architecture. In addition, there is a lack of widely used data and API standards for orchestrating the linking of multiple DTs.
- **Model complexity and run time:** the need to produce results within clinically realistic timescales to aid clinical decision making, provides a further challenge for integrated DTs, which can be addressed by creating surrogate models using AI.
- **Infrastructure:** the VHT infrastructure should be user-friendly and capable of handling large-scale data and complex models, while facilitating the interoperability with commercial platforms used in industry and clinics. The infrastructure should assist users in meeting the requirements regarding standardization and interoperability of their resources.

3. Ethical, legal and social barriers

- **Data privacy and security:** the sensitive nature of health data necessitates strict privacy and security measures to ensure responsible and ethical data sharing. Widespread uncertainty regarding the concept of anonymous data and national divergences regarding legal bases on data reuse further complicate the scenario.
- **Informed consent and transparency:** clear guidelines and procedures for obtaining informed consent from individuals for various forms of data use are (remain) essential. Additionally, transparency regarding the underlying assumptions, algorithms and potential biases in VHT models is crucial for building trust with society at large.
- **Equity and access:** ensuring equitable access to VHT technologies across diverse populations is crucial to avoid exacerbating health disparities.
- **Legal clarity and liability:** addressing legal clarity, certainty and liability is required to provide reassurance to developers, investors and healthcare providers regarding legal compliance, support and the allocation of responsibility in the event of any unintended consequences or harm arising from the use of this technology, including hospital downtime due to e.g. security issues.

4. Regulatory science barriers

- **Consolidated regulatory pathways:** the fragmentation of the regulatory decision-making landscape, and the absence of established standards and precedents for evaluating the safety and efficacy of the novel and complex VHT technologies, slow down their translation.
- **Validation data:** the lack of sufficient, accessible and high-quality data for VHT development limits the ability to develop comprehensive and credible models that can be effectively used for research, regulatory assessment, clinical applications and commercialization.

5. Economic and sustainability barriers

- **Funding and investment:** sustained funding and investment are essential for advancing VHT research, developing and maintaining its infrastructure as well as supporting the innovation framework, providing innovation hubs and training VHT innovation officers.
- **Business models and value proposition:** clear business models and a compelling value proposition are needed to incentivize participation of all stakeholders along the VHT value chain (including patients) and attract private investments, ensuring the long-term sustainability of the VHT ecosystem.
- **Open source conundrum:** while open-source licensing could enhance collaboration and streamline development, competitive funding strategies, institutional plans for commercialization, and investor preferences for exclusive rights can hinder its adoption. Achieving a balance between fostering open-source solutions and maintaining viable business models, including mechanisms for developer participation in profits, is essential to ensure development and maintenance of a high-quality, sustainable VHT infrastructure.
- **Skilled workforce:** training and retraining of the workforce, from technology developers, over regulatory experts to healthcare providers, is required to ensure presence of the necessary competencies to develop, handle or assess VHT technologies.
- **Specific reimbursement pathways:** the absence of established reimbursement pathways creates uncertainty, limiting the incentives for adoption. This challenge also affects the developers' ability to demonstrate financial value in the healthcare ecosystem.

6. Clinical integration and adoption barriers

- **Clinical validation and utility:** demonstrating the clinical validity and utility of VHT applications through rigorous studies and trials, communicated in clinical publications and guidelines, is crucial to show sufficient safety and benefits for gaining clinical and hospital buy-in and integrating these technologies into clinical practice.
- **Integration into existing workflows:** the practical challenge of integrating these technologies into current clinical workflows, as well as provisioning access to already existing data generating tools (wearables, devices), often deters adoption.
- **Interdisciplinary teams:** teams of healthcare professionals and medical technology experts are needed to integrate and adopt the variety of devices, instruments or services that use or deliver VHT applications acquired by healthcare providers.

7. Cultural and organisational barriers

- **Resistance to change:** some stakeholders may resist adopting new technologies as they involve changes to already established workflows, or because of skepticism, lack of knowledge or mistrust. Implementing proper change management processes will allow to prepare and support individuals, teams and leaders in making organizational change to embrace the VHT.
- **Education and training:** educating stakeholders, including patients, healthcare professionals, regulators and others, about VHT technologies, their applications and appropriate use, as well as their limitations is essential for fostering adoption and effective use in healthcare.
- **Geographical and organisational differences:** the use of VHT applications in the “real world” requires working with local constraints, which can differ among countries, among regions in a single country or even among organisations within the same region.

Addressing these barriers requires a multi-faceted approach involving collaboration among researchers, clinicians, patients, industry, policymakers and regulatory bodies. Overcoming these challenges is essential towards unlocking the transformative potential of the VHT and realizing a future of personalized, predictive, and preventative healthcare.

**PART 2: THE VISION OF
THE VIRTUAL HUMAN TWIN
AND HOW TO GET THERE**

The vision of the Virtual Human Twin

Taking into account the current healthcare, policy and innovation context, as well as the needs and challenges identified by the stakeholders across the VHT ecosystem, this resulted in the following high-level vision for the Virtual Human Twin.

A **Virtual Human Twin** is an integrated multi-level, -time, and -discipline digital representation of a body, organ, tissue or cell enabling the comprehensive characterisation of the physiological and the pathological state in its heterogeneity, allowing patient-specific predictions for the prevention, prediction, screening, diagnosis and treatment of a disease, as well as the evaluation, optimisation, selection, personalization, and de-risking of intervention options.

The Virtual Human Twin initiative represents a groundbreaking approach to addressing key challenges in healthcare, including rising costs, the growing demand for personalized medicine, and the need for more efficient healthcare systems. By leveraging advanced *in silico* technologies such as computer modelling, simulation, and artificial intelligence, supported by state-of-the-art computational infrastructure and data technologies, the VHT enables the creation of virtual representations of human physiology and pathology. These virtual models offer insights into disease progression across scales of time, space, and organ systems, paving the way for personalized, predictive, and preventive care, accelerating medical research, and improving support for clinicians, patients, and healthcare providers.

The **VHT initiative** emphasizes both generating new scientific knowledge and applying it to enhance clinical care. Its realization requires collaborative efforts at a European level, including the establishment of a dedicated VHT infrastructure. In order to achieve its core goals, the VHT initiative furthermore requires work on pooling resources and expertise, data sharing and interoperability, credibility and trust, as well as economic sustainability. As such, the VHT initiative will provide a systematic, ever-growing digital and quantitative representation of the actionable knowledge available on human pathophysiology. Its federated public infrastructure will enable the pooling of resources and assets (data, models, algorithms, computing power, storage etc.) to develop Digital Twins in healthcare and assess their credibility. A **collaborative, diverse, and engaged ecosystem** will facilitate the uptake of the VHT across all sectors and R&D phases, including clinical practice, with full respect of ethical, legal, and social considerations.

Realizing the vision of the VHT, requires development on a wide range of topics, starting with a need statement, and including technology, infrastructure, standards, regulatory processes, ELSI (ethical, legal and social issues), users, uptake, as well as business models and sustainability (Figure 4). Collaboration between researchers, clinicians, policymakers, and industry stakeholders is essential to establish robust technical solutions, ethical guidelines, and regulatory frameworks.

The VHT infrastructure that is described in this roadmap, is based on the extensive and inclusive ecosystem-centered process that was followed by the EDITH consortium, as described at the start of this policy brief. A tender process has been started by the European Commission, independently from the EDITH project, to build the VHT's advanced simulation platform²³.

Figure 4: Main elements of the VHT development, elaborated in detail in the full VHT roadmap.

The technological foundations of the Virtual Human Twin

Digital Twins consist of three core components²⁴: hardware, data management middleware, and software (Figure 5). Together, these elements form the backbone of the VHT applications, each playing a vital and interconnected role, working in harmony to bridge the physical and digital worlds.

Figure 5: Main components of a Digital Twin.

Hardware components

Hardware serves as the physical layer of a Digital Twin system, comprising medical imaging, sensors, actuators, devices, and computational infrastructure that capture and process real-world data. These components provide the critical foundation for creating digital replicas.

For example, consider a patient undergoing treatment for a cardiovascular condition. Wearable sensors, such as electrocardiogram (ECG) monitors, blood pressure cuffs, and oxygen saturation trackers, continuously collect data about the patient's physiological parameters whereas medical images provide insight into the overall status of the system. These data-generating hardware components act as the inputs of the Digital Twin, providing data that reflects the patient's cardiovascular function and overall health status.

In general, **data-generating hardware** includes medical imaging devices, wearable sensors, implantable medical devices, and environmental sensors, which collect patient-specific data such as physiological parameters, behavioural patterns, and environmental factors. Advanced technologies like micro-physiological systems (including organ-on-chip systems) and high-throughput omics platforms (including genomics) also contribute critical biological data for personalized healthcare applications.

In addition to data acquisition tools, the hardware layer incorporates **computational infrastructure** to support the processing needs of Digital Twins. Advanced computational infrastructure including high-performance computing, cloud platforms, and edge computing systems enable the execution of computationally intensive simulations, model training, and real-time analyses. These infrastructures are designed for scalability, ensuring they meet the demands of large-scale data processing, VHT simulations and collaborative research across distributed teams.

Middleware components

Middleware acts as an intermediary between hardware and software, enabling seamless data communication, integration, and management. This layer ensures that data collected from the hardware is processed, standardized, and made accessible to the software for further analysis and simulation.

In a hospital setting, for instance, multiple patients in the intensive care unit (ICU) are monitored using various medical devices that measure parameters such as heart rate, respiration, and glucose levels. Middleware aggregates and organizes this data, ensuring that it is standardized and consistent for use by the Digital Twin's software layer. This ensures that clinicians can access accurate and integrated data to support treatment decisions.

Software components

Software, also indicated with the term DT models, represents the analytical and predictive layer of Digital Twins. It leverages pre-existing knowledge on (patho-)physiology along with data provided by the hardware and middleware to create virtual models, conduct simulations, and perform predictive analyses to support informed decision-making.

Take the example of personalized treatment planning for a cancer patient. Digital Twin software can create a virtual model of the patient's tumour using imaging data, biopsy results, genetic screening information and sensor-collected biomarkers. By simulating how the tumour responds to different therapies, such as chemotherapy or radiation, the software helps oncologists identify the most effective treatment plan. This allows clinicians to optimize patient outcomes while minimizing adverse effects.

These DT models can range from population-level twins, which simulate the average behaviour of a group for applications like *in silico* (clinical) trials, to highly personalized twins tailored to individual patients. Different *in silico* (computational) technologies can be used to generate digital twin models. One approach is that of data-driven modelling, which relies on AI and machine learning to identify patterns and make predictions based on large datasets. The knowledge-driven modelling approach is grounded in scientific principles and computational simulations to explore physiological mechanisms and test hypotheses. However, most DT models combine data- and knowledge-driven approaches for more accurate and flexible representations of human physiology. The choice of modelling approach should be based on what is available in terms of data and knowledge related to the question of interest. These DT models operate within a defined context of use, ensuring that they are tailored to specific clinical applications and validated for reliability. The software layer supports tasks such as disease prediction, treatment planning, and resource optimization, enabling personalized and effective healthcare interventions.

The Virtual Human Twin infrastructure

The VHT roadmap provides a detailed description of the different elements that are required for building a successful VHT infrastructure that meets the ecosystem's needs. The VHT infrastructure should comprise three core components – **Catalogue, Repository, and Simulation Platform** – designed to enable the storage, management, access, and execution of data, models, and workflows essential to digital twin applications in healthcare²⁵ (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Schematic overview of the proposed use of the VHT infrastructure.

The **Catalogue** will act as the central gateway to digital twin resources, offering an intuitive interface for discovering and accessing datasets, models, and tools relevant to specific research or clinical needs. To ensure effective resource management, the catalogue should employ a robust metadata schema that captures key characteristics of each resource, such as provenance, interoperability, and standardized formats. Users can search the catalogue by keywords, metadata attributes, and relationships between resources, refining results to identify the most relevant assets. By linking related resources – such as datasets used to train specific models or models embedded within particular software tools – the catalogue can support the construction of complex workflows while adhering to FAIR principles, thus enhancing its utility across institutions and research communities.

The **Repository** will provide the secure storage infrastructure for the actual digital twin assets, including datasets, models, software, and documentation. Given the sensitivity of healthcare data, security and reliability are paramount, with robust measures such as encryption, access controls, and compliance with data protection regulations like GDPR. The repository should also ensure the integrity and traceability of resources by capturing their version history and provenance, allowing researchers to reproduce results and assess data quality. Its design should accommodate scalability, enabling it to meet the growing demands of the research and clinical communities. By storing data and models in standardized formats, the repository can promote interoperability and facilitate resource sharing across diverse applications. Finally, its federated architecture should ensure connections with existing initiatives and digital infrastructures, allowing the VHT to act as a one-stop-shop for building DTs.

The **Simulation Platform** will serve as the backbone of the VHT ecosystem, integrating hardware, software, and middleware networking resources to support the repository and catalogue while facilitating digital twin operations. Designed in collaboration with stakeholders and end-users, the platform should promote resource sharing, enhance collaboration, and ensure the privacy and security of sensitive data. The platform's federated architecture can connect multiple repositories and computing resources, enabling institutions to maintain control over their data while enhancing scalability and resilience by distributing computational loads. The platform's computing infrastructure should support diverse requirements, including high-performance computing (HPC) and cloud resources, while secure networking protocols safeguard data during transfer. The user-facing interface should be designed for accessibility, featuring intuitive tools and comprehensive training materials to support users with varying technical expertise. The platform architecture should be structured into layers: a frontend for user interfaces and visualization tools, middleware for identity and workflow management, and backend services for secure data storage and computational resource access.

Challenges in developing and operating the Virtual Human Twin infrastructure

The technical organisation, implementation and challenges related to the proposed VHT infrastructure are described in detail in the VHT roadmap. Here, a number of these challenges are mentioned.

- **Metadata complexity:** defining and maintaining interoperable metadata standards that capture provenance, syntax, semantics, and accessibility for diverse resources while ensuring consistency across the system.
- **Data integration and interoperability:** harmonizing data from multiple sources and ensuring seamless exchange between systems, models, and workflows, particularly across different scales (spatial, temporal).
- **Scalability:** designing the repository and simulation platform to handle increasing volumes and diversity of digital twin assets while maintaining performance and reliability.
- **Security and compliance:** ensuring robust data protection through encryption, secure networking, and adherence to privacy regulations, particularly when handling sensitive healthcare data.
- **Federated architecture management:** balancing the benefits of a federated system (data sovereignty and resilience) with the technical challenges of distributed computation and storage.
- **User accessibility:** developing intuitive interfaces and providing training resources to ensure the system is accessible to users with varying technical expertise. Interfacing with immersive technologies to enhance user experience.
- **Validation of models and workflows:** establishing rigorous validation protocols to ensure the accuracy and reliability of integrated multi-scale models and workflows.
- **Effective visualization and communication:** providing advanced visualization tools (e.g. virtual reality) and automated language processing to support decision-making and generate actionable insights for diverse audiences.

Artificial Intelligence plays a crucial role in the VHT by enabling the creation, optimization, and integration of digital twins, enhancing scalability and efficiency while addressing data gaps and facilitating user interactions. AI automates tasks such as image segmentation, accelerates simulations using surrogate models, and personalizes knowledge-driven models. Additionally, AI-driven recommendation systems streamline resource selection and integration, ensuring seamless interaction within the VHT. AI can generate synthetic data, harmonize diverse resources, and optimise computational workflows for cost-effective operations. Finally, Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Large Language Models (LLMs) enhance knowledge discovery by organizing resources, supplementing knowledge graphs, and generating user-specific reports tailored to clinicians or patients.

ELSI: legal, ethical and social imperatives

The vision of integrating Virtual Human Twin within the EU health systems necessitates a meticulous approach that not only considers technological advancement but also prioritizes the intricate legal, ethical, and social dimensions of this innovative initiative²⁶. These elements are integral, not peripheral, to the responsible development and implementation of VHT technology, ensuring its contribution to personalized medicine while safeguarding patient rights and societal values. As these aspects continuously evolve, the VHT infrastructure should include a standards and policy watch, as well as the necessary services to enable compliance.

Standards: the cornerstone of interoperability and trust

Standards form the bedrock of a robust and trustworthy VHT ecosystem, enabling data and model integration, facilitating interoperability, assuring data quality, and fostering confidence among stakeholders²⁷. Standardization is essential for the seamless exchange of data, integration of models, as well as for the development and implementation of reliable VHT applications. Standards evolve continuously, as technology and regulatory science do, and therefore they need to be constantly maintained and updated by domain-specific standardization bodies.

Key areas requiring standardization

- **Data formats and exchange:** standardizing data formats is paramount for ensuring compatibility and usability across the VHT infrastructure. Adhering to established standards such as those defined by standard defining organizations (SDOs) ISO, CEN/CENELEC, and IEC, or community standards when official standards from SDOs are not (yet) available, enables seamless integration of data from diverse sources²⁸.
- **Model representation and validation:** the credibility and trustworthiness of VHT models hinge on standardized methods for their representation and validation. Initiatives like Good Simulation Practice²⁹ (GSP) and standards such as ISO/TS 9491-1:2023³⁰ provide valuable guidance on best practices for model development, ensuring their reproducibility, reliability, and fitness for purpose.
- **Terminologies and ontologies³¹:** establishing a common language, through standardized terminologies and ontologies, is essential for effective communication and collaboration within the VHT ecosystem. The development and use of domain-specific ontologies for human physiology, pathology, and healthcare procedures, aligned with existing ones, facilitates clear understanding, data integration, and knowledge representation across different VHT components.
- **Software Interfaces:** standardizing application programming interfaces (APIs) and their interoperability ensures smooth communication and interaction between different software elements within the VHT infrastructure. This interoperability fosters modularity, facilitating the integration of new tools and technologies without disrupting existing workflows.

Regulatory science: guiding the Virtual Human Twin

Regulatory science is not merely a compliance process; it is the cornerstone of a safe, effective, and trusted VHT ecosystem, guiding innovation and ensuring that VHT technologies meet the highest standards of quality, safety and efficacy. It provides the framework for translating research into clinical practice by defining the rules and processes for the development, validation, and deployment of VHT solutions. As VHT technologies evolve, so must the regulatory science be guiding them, adapting to the unique characteristics and challenges posed by these novel technologies.

Key elements within regulatory science for the VHT

- **Clear regulatory pathways:** establishing clear and efficient regulatory pathways is essential to ensure that VHT technologies can be effectively evaluated, approved, and integrated into healthcare systems. This involves identifying which existing regulatory frameworks are applicable and, where necessary, developing new frameworks tailored to the specific challenges and opportunities presented by VHT. It is important to ensure that these pathways are not only robust, but also flexible, to adapt to rapidly evolving technologies.
- **Credibility assessment:** a central aspect of regulatory science is the establishment of rigorous and transparent methods for assessing the credibility of VHT models and simulations. This includes methods for verification and validation (V&V), and uncertainty quantification, ensuring the models are fit for their intended use. Frameworks such as ASME V&V 40-2018³², serve as benchmarks for assessing the credibility of predictive models, and provide valuable guidance for assessing the reliability and trustworthiness of VHT technology.
- **Data quality and governance:** ensuring the quality and integrity of data used in VHT development is essential for accurate and reliable outcomes. Regulatory science provides standards and guidelines for data collection, integration, annotation, validation, anonymization and security, which are critical for trust in the VHT. This includes addressing the challenge of data interoperability, ensuring that different data sources can be seamlessly integrated while maintaining privacy and security.

Health Technology Assessment: evaluating the Virtual Human Twin for healthcare integration

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) is a critical component for ensuring the value, effectiveness, and appropriate adoption of VHT technologies within healthcare systems. HTA actors play a vital role in bridging the gap between VHT development and real-world implementation, by rigorously assessing the clinical, economic, and societal impact of these technologies. They provide the necessary evidence to support informed decision-making by healthcare providers, payers, and policymakers.

Key aspects of HTA actors' role in the VHT

- **Evaluation of clinical and economic effectiveness:** HTA bodies assess the clinical effectiveness of VHT technologies by analysing their impact on patient outcomes, disease progression, and treatment efficacy. They also evaluate the economic impact, considering the cost of implementation, resource utilization, and long-term value for healthcare systems. This ensures that VHT solutions are not only safe and effective but also economically sustainable. HTA actors implement governance instruments to evaluate evidence, supporting the clinical and economic effectiveness of VHT technologies. They work to assure that VHT technologies bring value and benefit to healthcare systems and broader society.
- **Assessment of societal impact:** HTA considers broader societal implications, such as ethical considerations, equity of access, and impact on public health. This holistic approach ensures that VHT technologies are not only beneficial to individual patients but also aligned with societal values and needs.

- **Guidance for reimbursement and market access:** HTA findings are crucial for informing reimbursement decisions by payers and healthcare systems. They provide the evidence needed to determine which VHT technologies should be covered by insurance plans, and establish guidelines for their adoption and integration within clinical practice. HTA actors are involved in pre-commercial and value-based procurement of innovation which can be a key element in the strategic development of the VHT through demand-driven pathways and partnerships.
- **Collaboration with VHT developers:** effective communication and collaboration between VHT developers and HTA actors are essential for aligning expectations and generating the necessary evidence to support the adoption of VHT solutions. This collaboration allows for iterative refinement of VHT solutions.
- **Navigating the diverse landscape of HTA frameworks:** HTA actors must navigate the fragmented landscape of HTA frameworks and reimbursement pathways in different countries and regions. This involves understanding the different criteria, standards and required evidence for assessing digital health technologies. For example, different member states may have different decision-making processes for reimbursement that can delay patient access to VHT applications.

Legal landscape: a complex terrain requiring careful navigation

The sensitive nature of healthcare data and the potential impact of the VHT on medical decision-making demand a comprehensive understanding and adherence to a complex network of legal acts. A proactive engagement with regulatory bodies and health technology assessment actors is essential, incorporating legal requirements from the outset of VHT development and throughout its operational lifecycle.

Key legal and regulatory considerations

- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):** the cornerstone of data protection in the EU, the GDPR, imposes stringent requirements on the processing of personal data, particularly of sensitive data, such as health information. VHT implementation must prioritize data privacy and security, embedding robust data governance measures into the infrastructure design. Key considerations include data minimization, purpose limitation, data security, and the implementation of appropriate anonymization or pseudonymization techniques to safeguard patient confidentiality while enabling data use for VHT development and application.
- **European Health Data Space (EHDS):** the EHDS policy program, aiming to create a unified legal framework and interoperable data space for exchanging health data across the EU, presents both opportunities and challenges for VHT implementation. Aligning the VHT infrastructure with EHDS principles is crucial, particularly regarding the sharing and secondary use of health data.
- **Medical Device Regulation (MDR) / *In vitro* Device Regulation (IVDR):** the classification of VHT applications as medical devices or *in vitro* diagnostic devices under the MDR or IVDR respectively is contingent upon their intended use and the related risk for the patient. If Digital Twins are deployed for diagnosis, treatment recommendations, or other medical decision-making processes, they fall under the purview of the MDR. This entails demonstrating compliance with stringent safety and performance requirements, including rigorous clinical evaluation and validation processes to ensure patient safety and effectiveness.
- **AI Act:** the AI Act, designed to regulate the use of AI systems within the EU, has significant implications for VHT development and implementation. The Regulation categorizes AI systems based on risk levels, with high-risk ones, particularly those used in healthcare, subject to more stringent requirements. The VHT ecosystem must proactively monitor the evolution of the AI Act, ensuring compliance with its provisions for data quality, transparency, human oversight, and risk management.

- **Data sharing and reuse:** navigating the legal complexities of data sharing and reuse for VHT development is paramount. The European context with its varying interpretations of anonymization and pseudonymization across member states, leads to uncertainty and potential legal roadblocks for cross-border research and data use. A VHT “Code of Conduct” should be established to harmonize data reuse practices, ensuring ethical data governance while promoting innovation.
- **Intellectual Property (IP) rights:** clarifying ownership and licensing of VHT models and data upfront is crucial for fostering innovation and ensuring fair compensation for developers. While building the VHT infrastructure, it will be indispensable to develop a clear legal framework to address IP concerns while promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing within the VHT ecosystem.
- **Liability:** the potential for harm arising from VHT applications, such as misdiagnosis or inappropriate treatment recommendations given by VHT, necessitates a robust liability framework. The AI Act and the upcoming AI liability directive (will) play a key role in clarifying liability for AI systems, including those used in Digital Twins. Establishing clear lines of responsibility among developers, healthcare providers, and patients is essential for building trust and ensuring accountability.

Ethical considerations: placing patient well-being and societal values at the forefront

The potential of VHT to transform healthcare necessitates an ethical framework that guides its development and application, prioritizing patient well-being, and aligning with broader societal values.

Key ethical principles for VHT implementation

- **Informed consent and data privacy:** informed consent is the cornerstone of ethical data use, ensuring patients have a clear understanding of how their data will be used, or reused, for VHT development and application. Transparency regarding data collection, processing, storage, repurposing, and sharing is essential. Implementing robust data governance protocols, including appropriate anonymization or pseudonymization techniques, and providing mechanisms for patients to control their data are key to fostering trust and respecting patient autonomy.
- **Transparency and explainability:** the inherent complexity of VHT algorithms and models requires a commitment to transparency and explainability. Patients and healthcare providers should have a clear understanding of how VHT-driven conclusions are reached. The use of black-box AI models, lacking interpretability, raises concerns about accountability and potential biases, potentially undermining trust and hindering responsible clinical decision-making.
- **Equity and access:** ensuring equitable access to the benefits of VHT technology is a paramount ethical consideration. The VHT ecosystem must actively address potential biases in data and algorithms, promoting fairness and inclusivity in design and deployment. This includes considering factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and disability to ensure that VHT applications do not exacerbate existing health disparities.
- **Beneficence and non-maleficence:** the fundamental ethical principles of beneficence (doing good) and non-maleficence (avoiding harm) are central to VHT development and application. VHT technologies should be designed and deployed with the primary goal of improving patient well-being and healthcare outcomes while minimizing potential risks. This requires careful consideration of potential unintended consequences, rigorous validation of models and algorithms, and continuous monitoring of real-world outcomes to identify and mitigate any potential harms.

- **Accountability and responsibility:** establishing clear lines of accountability and responsibility for the development, deployment, and use of VHT technologies is crucial. This includes addressing potential challenges related, among others, to breaches of applicable legislation, unlawful data processing, lack of transparency and human oversight, algorithmic biases, and unintended consequences of VHT applications. Developing mechanisms for redress and ensuring that appropriate legal frameworks are in place to address liability concerns are essential for maintaining public trust and fostering responsible innovation.

Social implications: building a foundation of societal acceptance and trust

The integration of VHT technologies into healthcare practices hinges on societal acceptance and trust. Active public engagement, education, and open dialogue are vital for addressing concerns, dispelling misconceptions, and fostering confidence in the responsible development and use of these transformative technologies.

Key strategies for building societal trust in the VHT

- **Public engagement and education:** proactive and transparent communication about VHT technologies is essential for fostering societal understanding and acceptance. This includes developing accessible educational materials, organizing public forums, and engaging with the media to explain the potential benefits of the VHT, address common concerns, and dispel myths or misconceptions.
- **Co-creation and patient involvement:** empowering patients and citizens by involving them in the design and development of VHT applications is crucial for ensuring that these technologies align with societal values and meet real-world needs. Co-creation approaches promote transparency, build trust, and allow patients to play an active role in shaping the future of their healthcare.
- **Addressing ethical and social concerns:** open and honest dialogue about the ethical and social implications of the VHT and its applications is essential for building public confidence. This includes proactively addressing concerns related to data privacy, algorithmic bias, potential impact on the patient-physician relationship, and the equitable distribution of benefits.
- **Demonstrating value and benefits:** clear and compelling communication about the tangible benefits of VHT technologies is crucial for garnering public support. This includes highlighting successful use cases, showcasing positive patient outcomes, and emphasizing the potential of the VHT to improve healthcare quality, efficiency, and accessibility.

Uptake and sustainability of the Virtual Human Twin

Long-term sustainability of the VHT is critically linked to its uptake by a diverse set of users³³. It requires a collaborative and inclusive approach that involves all stakeholders, from researchers and clinicians to patients and policymakers. A **thriving and engaged ecosystem** is essential for the success of the VHT initiative. Cultivating a strong community that embraces the VHT vision and actively contributes to its development requires understanding the incentives for both VHT creators and consumers. Researchers and model developers are motivated by the prospect of accessing vast datasets, validating their models, and collaborating with a global community. Clinicians, on the other hand, seek demonstrable clinical benefits, improved patient outcomes, and enhanced decision-making tools. Addressing the **specific needs and expectations of each stakeholder group** is paramount for fostering their engagement and maximizing the impact of the VHT. Developing sustainable business models for the VHT is crucial for ensuring its long-term viability and continued development. Identifying potential revenue streams, exploring different (public and private) funding mechanisms, and establishing a **robust governance framework** will enable the VHT to operate sustainably and evolve to meet the changing needs of its users.

Uptake in industry

The VHT's potential for industrial applications is significant, offering a range of possibilities for generating revenue and advancing healthcare innovation, including through technology development and systems integration, data management and security services, R&D and clinical decision support, and through business integration and support. These models reflect the various ways stakeholders can engage with the VHT ecosystem, from using existing VHT tools and data for research to developing proprietary applications for healthcare providers.

- **Marketplace services:** creating a marketplace for DTHs, data, models, and computational resources can facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration. Revenue can be generated through transaction fees or subscription models.
- **Licensing and subscription models:** providing access to the VHT platform and its resources through licensing agreements or subscriptions. This enables healthcare organizations and industry stakeholders to leverage VHT capabilities without the need for extensive in-house development.
- **Consultancy services:** offering specialized consultancy services to assist organizations in tailoring VHT solutions to their specific needs. This could involve model development, data analysis, and integration with existing systems.
- **Data analysis services:** leveraging the vast amounts of data within the VHT infrastructure and federated repositories to provide advanced data analysis services. These services can support research, drug discovery, *in silico* clinical trial execution, and personalized medicine development.
- **Integration with EHR systems:** integrating the VHT with electronic health record (EHR) systems enhances data collection and analysis capabilities. This integration can facilitate more personalized and effective healthcare delivery by providing clinicians with real-time insights and predictions.
- **Development of stand-alone products:** spinning out stand-alone digital twin products from the VHT and passing them through the regulatory pipelines, will allow to integrate them in clinical workflows or operate them through service-based activities outside of the VHT.
- **Complementary skills collaboration:** incentivizing by creating revenue models through collaboration, enabling access to shared resources, enhancing innovation, and reducing costs in healthcare solution development.

Uptake in clinical practice

The clinical adoption of the VHT hinges on demonstrating its value in addressing unmet needs, improving patient outcomes, reducing costs, and enhancing care quality, as well as integrating it seamlessly into existing healthcare workflows:

- **Clinical decision support:** the VHT can act as a clinical decision support system, providing evidence-based insights, predictions, and personalized recommendations to assist in clinical decision-making regarding diagnosis, treatment planning, and patient management.
- **Predictive analytics:** utilizing patient-specific data and models, the VHT can identify individuals at risk of developing certain conditions. This allows for personalized preventive measures and proactive interventions, potentially leading to better health outcomes.
- **Personalized treatment planning:** the VHT enables the creation of tailored treatment plans based on individual patient characteristics, disease profiles, and responses to therapies. This personalized approach aims to optimize treatment efficacy and minimize adverse effects. Extended reality technologies (AR/VR) allow visualizing processes and procedures for patients and clinicians.
- **Training and education:** the VHT can serve as a valuable tool for training healthcare professionals. It provides realistic simulations and scenarios for practicing clinical skills, decision-making, and learning about new medical technologies. Extended reality technologies permit interactive sessions even in a remote manner, increasing the quality of education of the healthcare workforce.

Sustainability of a Virtual Human Twin infrastructure

In order to realize the full potential of the VHT initiative, sustainability of its infrastructure is key for its widespread adoption and impact. This infrastructure should prioritize interoperability and openness, enabling seamless data sharing and collaboration across the VHT ecosystem. **Leveraging existing European infrastructures**, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), offers a valuable foundation for developing a VHT infrastructure that addresses the specific needs and requirements of the VHT ecosystem. Establishing **clear governance mechanisms** is important to ensure effective decision-making and accountability among stakeholders. Building this dedicated infrastructure requires collaborative efforts from the European Commission, EU member states, research institutions, and the private sector. A **dedicated and diverse funding landscape** is required to guarantee sustainability. The successful incorporation of this infrastructure in a European Digital Innovation Consortium requires a collaborative effort involving the European Commission, EU member states, research institutions, healthcare organisations and industry stakeholders. The key elements for sustainability of the public infrastructure align with the principles of European research infrastructures or European digital innovation consortia.

- **European Commission funding:** continuous support from the European Commission through programs such as Horizon Europe and the Digital Europe Programme is crucial for sustaining the VHT's development and implementation. Other instruments that allow engaging a wide range of stakeholders including the European Commission and European member states, are that of a European Digital Innovation Consortium or a European partnership for VHT.
- **Member State contributions:** financial contributions from European member states are essential, recognizing the VHT's potential benefits for national healthcare systems, research, and innovation.

- **Public-Private partnerships:** collaborations between public institutions, research organizations, and industry partners can leverage combined resources and expertise, contributing to the VHT's financial sustainability.
- **Commercial revenues:** the VHT legal entity could take on the role of providing services, particularly in the area of systems integration (of VHT systems in hospitals) or business integration and support (consultancy and advisory services) on a fee-for-service basis, with the revenue invested back into the development, maintenance and extension of the VHT's public infrastructure.

**PART 3:
RECOMMENDATIONS FOR
THE VIRTUAL HUMAN TWIN**

Recommendations for the roll-out of the Virtual Human Twin

Based on the work described in the VHT roadmap, 30 recommendations have been formulated that address key areas crucial for the successful realisation of the VHT vision. These recommendations have been divided according to the major sections of the VHT roadmap (as shown in Figure 4). They acknowledge the need for synergies with and dependencies on other initiatives, encompassing research, legislation, regulatory frameworks, and ethical dimensions, to ensure the VHT's effective and responsible integration into the healthcare landscape. A timeframe for these recommendations is provided in the next section.

Need assessment of creators and consumers

- 1. Research and innovation:** to ensure that the Virtual Human Twin reaches its full potential, research and innovation (R&I) are paramount. This R&I should span a continuum from basic research, addressing fundamental knowledge gaps and the development of nascent technologies, to translational research, bridging the gap between laboratory findings and clinical applications. The scope of R&I should cover the creation of generic and population-specific Digital Twins as well as highly personalized Digital Twins, catering to diverse applications. Embracing blue-sky research will be crucial for breakthroughs and innovation, alongside the exploration of diverse use cases to demonstrate the VHT's broad applicability.
- 2. Prioritizing use cases to enhance VHT impact:** the identification, development, and delivery of high-impact validated use cases is important to demonstrate the practical value of the VHT across diverse clinical and scientific applications. Prioritization should be given to use cases that address key areas such as diagnostics, medical education and training, clinical decision support, therapy development, and intervention planning. The development of a demonstrator (such as the Virtual Brain Twin) showcasing the capabilities of the VHT in a specific area will be valuable for engaging stakeholders and demonstrating its potential. Selecting a diverse range of use cases will illustrate the VHT's versatility and broad applicability, particularly highlighting the transition from screening diseases to more complex stratified simulations. This approach ensures that the VHT is developed with a focus on real-world applications, maximizing its impact and adoption.
- 3. Enhancing clinical utility- a cornerstone for VHT adoption:** to ensure the VHT is embraced in clinical practice, demonstrating its clinical usefulness is paramount. This requires a rigorous assessment of its clinical effectiveness and usability. Following a co-creation approach, the conceptualisation and development of the VHT must be driven by a clear understanding of clinical needs, ensuring the VHT addresses real-world challenges and provides tangible benefits. Fostering dialogue and collaboration with clinicians throughout the development process will ensure the VHT is aligned with clinical workflows and priorities.

4. **Applications across the disease continuum - realizing the full potential of the VHT:** to maximize the impact of the Virtual Human Twin, it is essential to advance the understanding of how its solutions, products, and services can be applied across the entire disease continuum. This includes exploring its potential in prevention, treatment, and follow-up, spanning a wide range of applications from biomedical and clinical studies to therapy development and diagnostics. The VHT should not be confined to traditional healthcare settings but also encompass innovative care models such as remote care and self-care, empowering individuals to actively manage their own health. This comprehensive approach will unlock the full potential of the VHT, transforming healthcare from a reactive system to a proactive, personalized, and patient-centric model.

Virtual Human Twin technologies: basic building blocks

5. **Advancing *in silico* technologies for a robust, versatile and impactful VHT:** to fully realize the transformative potential of the VHT, substantial investment in the development of *in silico* technologies is crucial. This includes focusing on longitudinal and longer-term human health and disease modelling, capturing the long-term dynamic nature of human physiology. The development of multiscale models is essential for integrating knowledge across different levels of biological organization, from cells to organs to the whole body. Incorporating new data modalities beyond traditional clinical data will enrich the VHT, enhancing its predictive power. Omics integration will provide a comprehensive view of individual biological processes, enabling personalized insights into health and disease. AI will play a central role in the VHT, not only in data analysis and model generation but also in driving the interaction between AI and mechanistic modelling.
6. **Data-generating hardware addressing a critical need for VHT:** the development of advanced data-generating hardware technologies is essential for the progress of VHT applications. Disease-specific data, fit for modelling purposes, is currently lacking from traditional sources like hospitals. This data gap can be addressed by investing in wearable and implantable sensor technologies capable of providing real-time patient data. Micro-physiological system technologies present another avenue for generating high-quality human-relevant data by combining microfluidics with embedded sensors. These technologies provide a platform for investigating adverse drug effects and modelling specific organ functions, offering valuable insights for the development of VHT applications.
7. **Evidence generation for VHT development:** the development of robust and trustworthy VHT technologies hinges on the generation of comprehensive clinical, experimental, and digital evidence to support model building and validation. This process requires well-designed studies and clinical trials that first assess the technical validity of VHT solutions, followed by their clinical domains such as safety, efficacy, effectiveness, and usability. A deep understanding of the unmet needs of VHT early adopters and how these technologies will be implemented to address those needs is essential for generating relevant and impactful evidence. VHT technologies can be used to develop synthetic and open-access validation datasets, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility. This evidence generation process will be instrumental in building confidence among stakeholders, paving the way for wider adoption of VHT in healthcare.

- 8. Credibility is key to building trust in VHT technologies:** to foster trust and confidence in VHT technologies, establishing their credibility is essential. This involves a multi-faceted approach encompassing rigorous and transparent safety assessments and peer review/validation of methods to ensure scientific rigor and transparency. Clear procedures for verification and validation, for a well-defined question of interest and context of use, must be developed, drawing upon established ontologies to provide a standardized framework for credibility assessment. Uncertainty quantification plays a vital role in understanding the limitations of VHT predictions and enabling risk-informed decision-making. Addressing potential refutations and providing clear evidence to support the credibility of VHT findings will be crucial for gaining acceptance from stakeholders.

Virtual Human Twin infrastructure

- 9. Designing the VHT resource repository and simulation platform:** the design, construction, and continuous enhancement of the VHT resource repository and simulation platform are crucial aspects. It is imperative that this platform adheres to all applicable laws and regulations in Europe, particularly concerning data privacy and security. The platform should leverage distributed and federated computing, incorporating regional or country-specific nodes to ensure data sovereignty and efficient resource utilization. A federated authentication and authorization mechanism is essential to manage secure access and facilitate collaborative data sharing across the VHT ecosystem. In addition to security, the platform should prioritize interoperability, modularity, flexibility, scalability and extensibility to accommodate future growth and advancements in VHT technologies. Embracing the principles of Open Science, Open Source, and Open Data will foster collaboration, accelerate innovation, and enhance transparency and trustworthiness of the VHT platform.
- 10. Investing in a robust and adaptable IT infrastructure:** to ensure the longevity and continuous growth of the VHT, sustained support for the development, testing, and implementation of advanced and interoperable IT platform architectures is needed. This includes investments in computational infrastructure, cybersecurity, HPC, cloud services, and edge infrastructure to store, manage and process the vast amounts of data generated by the VHT. Continuous inclusion and updates of domain-specific services are crucial to enable advanced workflows and applications. Additionally, providing tools for seamless integration, to harness new technology and to visualize results is essential.
- 11. The future of the VHT - data availability and access:** for the VHT to reach its full potential, access to high-quality, annotated, and interoperable digital health data is paramount. The VHT initiative should work in conjunction with existing and developing (data) infrastructures and platforms, like the European Health Data Space. Standardized formats and semantics will be essential for interoperability and effective data analysis. Privacy of patients and their personal health data must be safeguarded, which can be achieved through anonymization, pseudonymization, and synthetic data generation. Data curation, certification, and quality control will ensure the reliability of the data, with data stewards and curators playing key roles.

12. Co-evolution of the VHT - a collaborative ecosystem for success: the VHT should not exist in isolation but actively co-evolve with existing digital services and research infrastructures. Embracing a global vision for the European life sciences research infrastructures, the VHT initiative should establish strong links to existing platforms, including ESFRI and EOSC, to avoid duplication and foster synergy. The VHT should leverage these ongoing efforts and available platforms, mapping them along with other commercial and open source modelling and computational infrastructures, to ensure efficient resource utilization and maximize impact. Long-term support is crucial, requiring engagement from national actors and networks. Continuous collaboration with other initiatives is necessary to create a thriving ecosystem for the advancement of the VHT.

13. Fostering collaboration - co-designing the VHT for optimal usability: to ensure the successful adoption of the VHT technology, a co-design approach including end-users and other stakeholders is essential. Interactive design sessions can foster inclusion, allowing stakeholders to provide feedback and contribute to the development of a user-friendly platform. This user-centric design places ease of use at the forefront through documentation, demos, and training materials tailored to specific user needs. A strong emphasis on user experience and usability testing will ensure the platform's functionality aligns with the needs and expectations of diverse stakeholders. The development of an automated one-stop-shop catalogue can streamline access to resources and best practices, reducing barriers between research and practice. This participatory approach emphasizes communication and transparency by using clear language to communicate design processes, composition, and best practices to user groups.

ELSI, standards and regulatory aspects

14. Enabling a robust regulatory landscape for VHT: to effectively enable the safety, efficacy, trustworthiness, performance, and risk management of the VHT from its early stages of development, it is crucial to enhance the clarity of the regulatory landscape. This can be achieved through a credibility-by-design evolutionary framework that prioritizes the establishment of clear standards, approaches, tools, and techniques. Key elements include the implementation of a comprehensive regulatory framework, training and verification labs, and resources to assist in the creation of technical dossiers for certification. Robust validation and verification infrastructure is critical, as is the ability to assess data and model credibility. Ensuring data accuracy for validation and providing clear information about data accuracy will be crucial for building trust and ensuring the reliability of VHT outcomes. The establishment of dedicated sandboxes is also recommended to encourage innovation and accelerate the adoption of VHT technology.

15. Prioritizing standards for a unified and interoperable VHT: the VHT will heavily rely on standardization to guarantee interoperability. This includes well-defined and long-term maintained metadata standards, consistent terminologies, and efficient input procedures for quality assurance. Embracing ISO and IEC standards, harmonizing and unifying existing standards where applicable, and prioritizing standards-based interoperability will ensure the VHT's credibility and widespread adoption. Establishing best practices and consensus procedures, particularly within

mature communities that lack fixed standards, will be crucial. The development of clear guidelines for reporting and development, including standard operating procedures, will promote best practice sharing. This approach will ensure data can be seamlessly integrated and modelling results effectively processed and validated.

- 16. Navigating the legal landscape - ensuring compliance and adoption within the VHT:** to ensure the successful implementation of the VHT within the European Union, proactive monitoring and harmonisation of relevant EU and national legislation is necessary. The VHT platform should be designed to facilitate legal compliance, incorporating features and tools that help users identify and adhere to applicable regulations. This involves developing a clear accountability framework that outlines liability, provides reassurance, and establishes responsibility through guidelines and a code of conduct for VHT users. It is crucial to identify and address challenges within existing European legislation (e.g. AI Act, MDR, GDPR) that might hinder the certification and adoption of VHT solutions in industry and clinical settings. A unified EU-wide approach, or at the very least, careful monitoring of national laws and recognition of differentiation across Member States will be necessary to promote legal certainty and ensure seamless collaboration.
- 17. IP and the VHT, a foundation for collaboration:** establishing common ground regarding IP rights management and the protection of trade secrets is crucial for fostering trust and collaboration among VHT stakeholders. Additionally, the implications of software license's choices should be carefully evaluated to balance the need for open access with the protection of IP, an element that is important to facilitate the uptake of the platform and its application by start-ups and larger industrial players. Licensing frameworks operating under fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory terms, would ensure broad accessibility while compensating innovators. A comparable approach could be applied to the VHT ecosystem where specific foundational AI tools or methods are essential for interoperable and scalable systems.
- 18. The role of health technology assessment in VHT - ensuring value and efficiency:** innovation adoption instruments, like pre-commercial procurement, innovation procurement, innovation partnerships and value-based procurement, enable evidence generation, the analysis of the impact of VHT on clinical cost structures and potential reimbursement pathways. A comprehensive innovation adoption process will facilitate translation of VHT research into practice. This includes pro actively engaging with payers to demonstrate the synergies, value and cost-effectiveness of VHT applications across the value chain. Harmonizing approaches across VHT adopters and Member States will be key to unlocking the competitive advantage and leadership potential of the European VHT initiative and pave the way for its wider adoption, improving healthcare outcomes and promoting sustainable healthcare systems.
- 19. Building trust in VHT - ethical considerations:** the future of the VHT requires sustained efforts to build trust among users, recognizing the ethical complexities of this emerging technology. While VHT offers strong potential to increase fairness and equality in healthcare, guaranteeing digital human rights and equitable access is paramount and will need to be pursued constantly and attentively. Data ownership and models, including the role of altruism, will require careful consideration to ensure responsible development and utilization of the VHT.

Continued research and open discourse on the ethical challenges and principles related to VHT, such as identity, human enhancement and technology dependence, are essential. A multi-disciplinary ethics-by-design process will ensure ethical considerations are fully embedded within the design and operation of the VHT.

20. Embedding responsible research and innovation in the VHT: to ensure the responsible development of the Virtual Human Twin, the genuine collaboration with Social Sciences and Humanities is crucial. This will increase stakeholder inclusion and reflexivity within the ecosystem. In addition, it will provide valuable insights into the societal impact of VHT, ethical considerations, and potential challenges related to user adoption and trust. Effective communication and dissemination strategies are essential, tailored to the specific needs and interests of various stakeholder categories. Bringing together experts from diverse fields will facilitate a holistic understanding of the complex technical, social, and ethical aspects of VHT development across the ecosystem.

Users and inclusiveness

21. Creating an inclusive VHT ecosystem: for the Virtual Human Twin to successfully integrate into healthcare systems, it is crucial to foster an active and outgoing ecosystem that embraces diverse perspectives. This involves proactively gathering feedback from all stakeholders, including citizens, patients, industry professionals, healthcare providers, and scientists into the VHT development, design and materials. Co-creation with societal partners, raising awareness of VHT potential, and empowering users through accessible support mechanisms will build trust and promote wider adoption. Embracing innovative educational approaches will be key to fostering a broader understanding of the VHT, while leveraging advanced technologies, such as extended reality and AI, will facilitate user interactions. A robust support system encompassing access for all, dedicated researcher support, user-friendly tools like wizards, mapping tools, as well as dedicated training and workshops will further strengthen the VHT ecosystem.

22. Promoting clinical and patient uptake of VHT: to ensure the successful adoption and integration of VHT technologies into clinical practice, it is essential to prioritize stakeholder engagement and address the needs of clinical end-users throughout the development cycle. Co-creation with clinicians and patients, combined with well-defined incentives, can build trust and foster collaboration. These incentives should focus on delivering clear clinical benefits such as addressing unmet needs, improving patient outcomes, reducing costs, and enhancing care quality. Practical challenges, including data privacy, legal and ethical concerns, and cost implications, must be systematically addressed with robust mechanisms and transparent communication. Additionally, inclusion in clinical guidelines and offering tools and services aligned with clinical workflows, such as seamless integration with hospital systems and (immersive) patient engagement tools can further demonstrate the VHT's relevance. Outreach efforts, including educational programs and representation at clinical events, are vital to increase awareness and engagement. Finally, empowering clinicians through leadership roles and incorporating patient-centred design principles will strengthen trust and ownership, fostering widespread acceptance and accelerating the VHT's integration into healthcare systems.

- 23. Ensuring equitable access to the VHT:** the Virtual Human Twin should be accessible to individuals of all ages, genders, ethnicities, socioeconomic statuses, and disabilities. This will require fostering digital literacy and promoting equitable access to high-quality healthcare. To ensure the VHT is representative of diverse populations, it is crucial to incorporate data from rare diseases, special populations, ageing populations, and individuals residing in developing countries. Access to VHT technology will empower individuals to manage their health through personal health forecasting, improving health outcomes for all. Immersive technologies coupled to VHT applications can play an important role to ensure full appreciation of VHT results and lower barriers to adoption.
- 24. Communicating the VHT - reaching diverse audiences:** the Virtual Human Twin initiative requires a multifaceted communication strategy to reach diverse audiences across the European Union. Information should be disseminated in all EU languages to ensure inclusivity and accessibility. Engaging science communication experts can help translate complex scientific concepts into easily understandable language for the public. A combination of communication channels, including blogs, social media, science fairs, and interactive events like “science nights” will foster broader public awareness and understanding of the VHT. Developing user-friendly visualization tools will assist VHT developers and users in making the obtained results more accessible and engaging for a wider range of stakeholders. Citizen science initiatives can also be incorporated to promote public participation and engagement in VHT research.
- 25. Training the future VHT workforce:** to fully realize the potential of the Virtual Human Twin in transforming healthcare, comprehensive education and training programs are essential for all stakeholders. This includes incorporating training on digital technologies, including AI and computational modelling, into all healthcare-related degrees. Existing healthcare professionals and providers require retraining to acquire foundational knowledge of the VHT and its practical applications, enabling them to confidently work with this emerging technology. This widespread upskilling will foster a workforce capable of effectively contributing to and benefiting from VHT advancements, facilitating its seamless integration into clinical practice. As the VHT evolves, new professional roles could emerge focused on liaising between organisations and the VHT, such as VHT innovation officers.

Sustainability

- 26. Incentivizing the uptake of a credible VHT platform:** to ensure the sustainability of the VHT platform, it is crucial to incentivize its adoption in new developments while promoting the reuse of existing efforts, including data and models. This can be achieved through establishing clear governance mechanisms and implementing incentives for sharing resources such as harmonization and standardization tools, and promoting international cooperation to broaden the VHT knowledge base. Developing measures and metrics to track and reward resource sharing, evaluating model quality, and emphasizing fairness and accessibility will further support the platform’s long-term maintenance, longevity, and affordability.

27. Stimulating VHT commercialization: to accelerate the development of commercial activities around the VHT, establishing a robust marketplace is essential. This should provide a range of options to facilitate the exchange of VHT-related resources while ensuring the protection of IP rights. Developing diverse and sustainable business models will ensure long-term scalability and growth. Thoroughly understanding the business case of future adopters, including their willingness to pay for VHT services, is essential. Drawing insights from existing commercial infrastructures can provide valuable guidance in shaping the VHT marketplace and business models, and foster the VHT's successful integration into the healthcare ecosystem.

28. Investment strategy for the VHT: to ensure the successful development and implementation of the VHT, continuous, robust and diverse sources of support; both public and private, are essential. This support will facilitate a wide range of activities from existing platform maintenance, over the integration of new models and modalities, to ensuring legal compliance. A long-term investment strategy by the EU, including new EU calls for proposals, will attract multi-funder contributions and encourage co-investment from Member States and private partners in developing the VHT infrastructure and applications. Moreover, securing long-term funding for staff and promoting resource reuse will further contribute to the sustainability and advancement of the VHT ecosystem.

29. Integrating the VHT into the European infrastructure landscape: European policymakers should champion policy innovation to accelerate VHT development and adoption. The VHT's ambitious scope requires its integration into the European Infrastructure landscape. A decentralized approach is recommended, establishing national nodes to promote collaboration and resource sharing across Europe (*cf.* EOSC). Establishing the VHT as a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium or forming a dedicated European Partnership for the VHT will provide a sustainable framework for its long-term development, implementation and ecosystem engagement. This necessitates the active involvement of EU Member States as well as public and private partners to pool resources, expertise, and infrastructure, fostering collaboration across national borders.

30. The importance of environmental sustainability for the VHT: the development and deployment of the VHT needs to include careful consideration of its environmental impact. Minimizing the environmental footprint of the VHT infrastructure requires examining the energy consumption associated with data storage, processing, and model execution. This necessitates adopting sustainable practices in data centre operations and exploring energy-efficient algorithms and hardware architectures. Embracing the principles of Planetary Health, the VHT should strive to contribute to a healthier planet, recognizing the interconnectedness between human health and the environment. This underscores the importance of applying a "sustainability triangle" approach to VHT development, encompassing environmental, social, and economic considerations to ensure its long-term viability.

A tentative timeline of activities

The recommendations discussed in the previous sections are frequently inter-dependent and will only be realized through a gradual roll-out over time. In Figure 7 and Table 1, a proposal is made to pace the work for **realizing the VHT across the coming 10 years**, divided into the following 3 phases:

- **PHASE 1 (2025-2028, short term)**: building the foundations and demonstrating potential.
- **PHASE 2 (2029-2031, middle-long term)**: integration and continued investment.
- **PHASE 3 (2032-2034, long term)**: deployment (in the hospital).

The starting point for the proposed VHT activities is, as explained in the first section of this policy brief, a wide range of available technologies, data sets, community initiatives, standards etc.. Most of the work is done at lower technology readiness levels, but some DT applications are already used in clinical practice today. Given the diversity of developments and maturity levels, the proposed timeline is a rather fluid one that cannot - and should not - be interpreted strictly.

Several of the activities listed in the early phases, such as ecosystem engagement, communication, policy watch and use case development, will require **sustained efforts throughout** the later phases too. The work indicated in a particular phase is contingent on the successful realization of the work in earlier phases (milestones), such as the presence of a functioning VHT simulation platform at the start of phase 2. At the same time there are dependencies to a range of developments that are not strictly related to the VHT but are relevant to the different elements including technologies (e.g. AI, sensors), infrastructure (EHDS and other infrastructures), and ELSI (acts, regulations). These dependencies might expedite or delay the roll-out of certain activities mentioned in the recommendations.

Figure 7: Timeline for the VHT.

Table 1: Timeline for VHT activities (p.53).

Activities	Phase	Recommendations
Building the foundations and demonstrating potential		
Enabling technologies		
Technology development for VHT (including AI/ML and advanced modelling capabilities)	1-3	1,4,5,6
Platform realization for DT resource organization, creation and sharing	1	6,7,9,26
Federated structure of data sharing (including EOSC) and secure processing environments in connection with the EHDS	1-2	9,12,29
Demonstration of potential		
Prototyping with small-scale pilots with key stakeholders (e.g. specific clinical pathways, patient groups, and clinical experts)	1-2	2,3,22
Real-world feasibility check, evaluate and foster user acceptance among key stakeholders (clinicians, patients, VHT developers)	1-3	2,18,22,23,24
Continued ecosystem development, early uptake and targeted incentivization	1-3	20,21,24,26
Establishing clear credibility assessment processes and economic feasibility checks via policy pilots	1-2	7,8,14,18,27
Regulatory and policy		
Member state engagement	1-3	18,28
ELSI preparatory policy watch and analysis	1-3	16,19
Alignment with national/European data-protection laws (e.g. GDPR, IP, medical devices) and emergent guidelines on AI in healthcare	1-3	16,17,19
Development of VHT-specific regulatory processes and standards, enabling faster access of DTs to market	1-3	8,14,15,18
Integration and continued investment		
Federated structure and secure processing environment		
EOSC-enabled federated data spaces with data sovereignty and cross-border exchange	2	12,29
EHDS enabled health data and anonymization standards and interoperability	2-3	11,12,29
Pilot implementation and validation		
Large-scale pilots with real-life "stress tests" in multiple hospitals/regions	2-3	2,3,22
Validation of effectiveness for regulatory and clinical acceptance	2-3	3,7,14,22
Gradual integration of real-time analytics, access to patient data vaults for personalized applications	2	5,6,23
Establishment of EDIC for VHT		
Foster continued synergy among academia, industry, and healthcare providers	2-3	10,13,22
Support services in identity management, resource valuation using tokens, data provenance, etc.	2-3	9,11
Concrete and VHT-specific standards and legislation across member states, also by means of a specific Code of conduct	2-3	15,17
Demonstration of Return on Investment	2-3	18,25,27,28
Deployment		
Deployment in hospital and health systems		
Enterprise-grade VHT infrastructure	3	9,10,27,30
Larger health network adoption	3	23,25,26
Maturation of ecosystem and ongoing evolution		
A robust ecosystem of stakeholders, including services providers, specialized analytics vendors, and AI solution integrators	3	21,24,25
General acceptance & economic return		
Broad stakeholder trust through documented outcomes (improved care, lower costs, less medical professional workload)	3	20,24,30
Mature regulatory frameworks towards mainstream reimbursement and widespread commercial offerings	3	14,17,18,26,27

Many of the recommendations and dependencies outlined in the following sections are expected to be effectively facilitated through the EOSC EU node, launched in October 2024.

- **Access to High-Performance Computing (HPC) Resources:** the EOSC EU node provides access to state-of-the-art HPC resources, including high-powered servers and specialized software.
- **Interoperability and Data Sharing:** by promoting FAIR principles, the EOSC EU node enhances interoperability and facilitates seamless data sharing.
- **Advanced AI and Machine Learning Tools:** the platform offers cutting-edge AI and machine learning tools that can be used to train VHT models, analyse large datasets, and generate predictions related to human health and disease.
- **Secure and Reliable Infrastructure:** built on a robust and scalable foundation, the EOSC EU node ensures secure and reliable infrastructure for storing and processing sensitive VHT data, safeguarding patient privacy and maintaining data integrity.

Recommendations for the stakeholders of the Virtual Human Twin ecosystem

This section focuses on the role of the various stakeholders in the VHT ecosystem. Recommendations are grouped by stakeholder groups to identify areas in which each of them can contribute to the successful development and roll-out of the VHT.

European Commission

- **Establish dedicated funding and deployment programs:** dedicate funding specifically for advancing VHT research, development, standardization and deployment. This includes supporting basic research on identified knowledge gaps, translational research efforts, and projects with varying technology readiness levels. Funding should cover both generic/population-specific and personalized Digital Twins, as well as the maintenance of the underlying infrastructure and standards. Prioritize research and innovation in developing, testing, validating, and verifying advanced VHT technologies while ensuring synergy with existing digital services and capabilities at the European level. Create a European Partnership for VHT.
- **Champion a European VHT initiative:** continue to champion the further development and deployment of a comprehensive Europe an VHT initiative to accelerate the best use of technologies in healthcare, taking advantage of existing European VHT champions and assets. This includes fostering a deeper understanding of AI-based and simulation tools among healthcare providers, clinicians, as well as an understanding of clinical and patient needs among VHT researchers and developers. The European Commission's initiative involves procuring a *Platform for Advanced Virtual Human Twin Models*, showcasing its commitment to funding training and new research and innovation in this crucial area.
- **Promote interaction with existing EU-level initiatives:** ensure the VHT initiative aligns with other relevant European initiatives like the European Health Data Space and others to leverage existing infrastructure and facilitate data sharing. Support federated infrastructures in digital health and research enhancing interoperability and building of VHT.
- **Support and take decision on the European Digital Infrastructure (EDIC) for the VHT:** support the design and coordinate the implementation of a new EDIC to support the VHT, on the basis of a request formulated by at least three Member States.

EU Member states

- **Support national and regional VHT initiatives:** encourage and fund regional and national initiatives, including dedicated centres, grassroots projects, and funding programs, that promote the development of Digital Twins in healthcare. This should include mapping and refining these initiatives at the member state level to foster collaboration and optimize resource allocation.
- **Communicate and disseminate funding options:** create awareness on the possible funding pathways so that the VHT ecosystem can understand when and how they can leverage the different funding options, according to each country's strategic objectives.
- **Foster collaboration with the European VHT platform:** align national healthcare strategies with the development of the European VHT platform, facilitating data sharing and promoting the adoption of VHT technologies within national healthcare systems. Co-establish the European Partnership and EDIC for VHT.
- **Engage in federated governance:** open the discussion on federated governance to harmonise and facilitate cross-country regulations and VHT use.

Research community

- **Address fundamental research challenges:** focus on research to bridge foundational gaps in statistics, mathematics, and computing related to Digital Twins. This involves conducting rigorous research on model development, validation, and verification, as well as advancing methods for data generation, including, but not limited to, real-time simulations, multi-scale modelling, uncertainty quantification, and decision-making using Digital Twins.
- **Develop and share VHT resources:** contribute to building the VHT knowledge base by developing, validating, and sharing data, models, algorithms, and good practices. This can be achieved by actively contributing resources to the VHT infrastructure.
- **Address unmet stakeholder needs:** engage with all stakeholders to develop fit-for-purpose Digital Twins in a co-creation process, aligned with end-user needs and workflows. Implement high-impact validated use cases in clinical practice, prioritizing low hanging fruits with clinical champions to foster broader end-user engagement and uptake.
- **Integration with broader EU4Health objectives:** the VHT research field should align with EU4Health objectives, such as enhancing healthcare resilience, promoting equitable access to healthcare, and fostering the digital transformation of health systems. Integration with these broader goals will ensure the VHT contributes to a unified and impactful health strategy across the EU.

Industry

- **Engage in public-private partnerships:** collaborate with research institutions and public entities to accelerate VHT development and translation into practical healthcare solutions.
- **Explore VHT-based business models and VHT intermediary businesses:** identify and develop viable business models around VHT technologies, such as providing VHT-as-a-Service, developing VHT-powered software solutions for healthcare providers, creating personalized healthcare applications for individuals or taking part in intermediary businesses. This can involve collaborating with other stakeholders to establish a VHT marketplace where resources and services can be exchanged; in synergy with existing commercial activities.
- **Contribute to standardization efforts:** actively participate in defining and implementing standards for VHT data, metadata, models, and workflows to ensure interoperability and facilitate wider adoption of VHT technologies.

Healthcare providers

- **Engage in collaborative research:** participate actively in collaborations with VHT developers to provide clinical insights, define priorities, and guide the design of solutions that address real-world patient needs and integrate seamlessly into existing workflows.
- **Advocate for training and tools:** advocate for and participate in the development of training programs and user-friendly tools that simplify the interpretation of VHT-generated data, ensuring healthcare professionals are equipped to utilize the technology effectively in clinical practice.
- **Contribute to validation efforts:** support and contribute to rigorous clinical trials and validation studies to establish the impact of VHT on patient outcomes, cost-efficiency, and clinical processes, while addressing concerns about data security, algorithmic bias, and patient privacy.

Regulatory bodies and standard defining organizations

- **Develop VHT-specific regulatory pathways:** establish clear regulatory guidelines and pathways for the development, validation, and clinical use of VHT applications, ensuring patient safety and data privacy. This might involve establishing sandboxes for testing and evaluating VHT applications in a controlled environment.
- **Develop VHT-specific standards:** clear definitions for VHT software components and uniform standards for data formats, metadata, terminologies/ontologies, and workflows are essential to streamline approval processes, enhance interoperability, and support reproducibility.
- **Collaborate with international organizations:** participate in international efforts to harmonize regulatory approaches to VHT, promoting a globally consistent and robust framework for its development and use.

Payers, buyers and Health Technology Assessment actors

- **Utilize innovation adoption instruments:** HTA bodies and payers should leverage tools like pre-commercial procurement and value-based procurement to generate evidence, evaluate cost structures, and establish reimbursement pathways for VHT technologies.
- **Standardize evaluation and payment models:** clear criteria for assessing clinical and economic value should be developed alongside innovative payment mechanisms, such as value-based agreements, to address long-term uncertainties and support adoption.
- **Ensure equitable access and harmonization:** policies must promote affordability, accessibility, and harmonized evaluation strategies across Member States to unlock the full potential of VHT and improve healthcare outcomes.

Ethical, legal, and social sciences experts

- **Conduct comprehensive assessment of ethics and social implications:** continuously assess the ethical implications of VHT development and deployment, focusing on issues such as data privacy, informed consent, human oversight, bias in algorithms, and potential societal impacts.
- **Develop ethical guidelines and codes of conduct:** develop and promote ethical guidelines and codes of conduct for all stakeholders involved in VHT research, development, and application. This includes addressing the ethical and legal aspects of reusing and integrating data for VHT development.
- **Engage in public dialogue:** facilitate public dialogue on the ethical and societal implications of VHT to ensure societal needs, values and concerns are carefully considered, transparency is promoted, and trust relationships are established and maintained.

Patients and the public

- **Active participation in VHT development:** encourage patients and the public to actively participate in shaping the VHT by providing feedback on its development, raising concerns, and contributing to discussions on ethical, legal and social issues. Patient perspectives are crucial in ensuring that the VHT is developed and used in a way that aligns with their values and needs.
- **Education and awareness:** promote education and awareness programs to inform the public about the potential benefits, risks, and ethical considerations associated with VHT. Use immersive technologies coupled to VHT technologies to lower the barriers for access and understanding.

The successful realization and roll-out of the VHT hinges on a collaborative and coordinated approach from all stakeholder groups. These recommendations provide a starting point for addressing the technical, infrastructural, ethical, legal, and societal challenges associated with the VHT's development and governance, ensuring its responsible integration into the future of healthcare.

References

- 1 Ezekannagha et al. Nutrition Journal (2020) 19:96. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12937-020-00612-1>
- 2 <https://zenodo.org/communities/edith-csa>
- 3 <https://doi.org/10.17226/26894>
- 4 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-virtual-human-twins-initiative>
- 5 <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/policy-issues/the-future-of-health-systems.html>
- 6 OECD (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1787/1e53cf80-en>.
- 7 OECD/European Commission (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1787/b3704e14-en>.
- 8 <https://www.mydigitwin.nl/>, partially funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO)
- 9 <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- 10 Additional examples of digital twins and relevant resources are provided in the roadmap as use cases, user stories, success stories and EDITH realizations.
- 11 Pharmacologenic twin: Björnsson et al. Genome Medicine 12:4, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-019-0701-3>, Copyright CC BY 4.0.
- 12 Immune Simulator: <https://www.combine-group.org/>
- 13 Cancer twin: https://permedcoe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/PerMedCoE_2ndPR_2023.pdf
- 14 Brain Twin: Hashemi et al., IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering, 14, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RBME.2025.3562951> , <http://www.ebrains.eu>
- 15 Heart Twin: Roney et al. Interface Focus, 13:6, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsfs.2023.0038> , <https://www.sems.qmul.ac.uk/staff/c.roney/research/>
- 16 Glycemic twin: Uyttendaele et al. BioMed Eng OnLine 18:102, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12938-019-0720-8>. Copyright CC BY 4.0
- 17 Liver twin: <https://team.inria.fr/simbiotx/>
- 18 Bone twin: Aldieri et al. Comput Methods Programs Biomed. 240:107727, 2023. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2023.107727>. Copyright CC BY-NC-ND 4.0
- 19 For a detailed description, see roadmap PART 1, chapter 6.
- 20 MarketsandMarkets report 2023
- 21 MarketsandMarkets report 2023, based on the following sources: US Census Bureau, European Commission, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), CDC, CMS, World Bank, Digital Twins Consortium, European Commission, AHA, National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), NIH, WHO, Eurostat, P-MEC News, Interviews with Experts, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis.
- 22 Mario Draghi report: The future of European competitiveness (Part A & B), 2024
- 23 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/tender-details/docs/16cc3c6a-844a-42d4-9746-dcc7444b8001-CN/Technical%20Specifications_EC-CNECT-LUX-2024-OP-0014_Advanced%20VHT%20modelling%20platform_V1.pdf.
- 24 For a detailed description, see roadmap PART 2.
- 25 For a detailed description, see roadmap PART 3.
- 26 For a detailed description, see roadmap PART 4.
- 27 For a detailed description, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10492795>, <https://fairsharing.org/4787> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10524794>.
- 28 ISO 20691:2022 Biotechnology: <https://www.iso.org/standard/68848.html>
- 29 <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48284-7>
- 30 ISO/TS 9491-1:2023 Biotechnology: <https://www.iso.org/standard/83516.html>
- 31 An ontology is a set of terms and their corresponding relations that represent the entities in that subject area
- 32 ISBN: 9780791872048; currently transformed into an international ISO/IEC draft standard: IEC/PWI 62-5.
- 33 For a detailed description, see roadmap PART 5.

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